

Teacher solidity in the digital age and its effect on the effectiveness of primary school management

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ABSTRACT

Often an era affects a person's lifestyle in attitude. The attitude of solidity in the digital age is questionable because of its role in the effectiveness of school management. Some other members still believe in contributing to its effectiveness. To overcome these confusions and doubts, research is needed to test whether solidity still plays a role in improving management effectiveness. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of teacher solidity on the effectiveness of primary school management. Data were collected using quantitative methods. The data collection technique is to use questionnaires. The data were analyzed through Pearson product moments and t-tests. The results of the interpretation of research data showed that teacher solidity has a direct positive effect on the effectiveness of primary school management. The assessment of the results of the study emphasized that solidity cannot be ignored although it is still necessary to have the individual skills of teachers to face the digital age.

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1. INTRODUCTION

National education requires the quality of institutions at every level. The quality of the educational institution requires the effectiveness of management [1] at all levels including primary schools [2]. Achieving quality education management requires good planning, supervision and evaluation [3]; elementary school should go as it should. Likewise, the school management information system must run optimally [4]–[6]. Management effectiveness also needs to be supported by stakeholders' understanding of laws and regulations and government regulations on education [7]. Stakeholders' understanding of quality management in school management needs to be maintained [8]. Maximizing equity in teacher distribution needs to be done [9]. The ability (competence) and example of the principal in school management, the allocation of sufficient education funds in school management is an important thing that must be considered. Stakeholder appreciation of school management can be seen from the participation of the community in improving the quality of school management. Increasing the solidity, sincerity, and seriousness of teachers in improving the quality of school management [10], and increasing culture of quality stakeholders (school community and school community/committee) are an indicator of effectiveness in school management [11].

Various efforts have been made in order to improve the management of elementary schools in Bengkulu City, Indonesia. However, the quality of education has not shown an even improvement. Some schools showed relatively encouraging quality improvements, but others were quite concerning. One of the

indicators of this lack of effectiveness is indicated, since the scores of students' national examinations for various fields of study at the primary school level have not shown a significant improvement. The decline in the quality of graduates may be related to the perception of teachers who have nothing in common about the importance of solidity in management. Teachers who do not have the same perception of the importance of solidity can interfere with the achievement of school quality management. The perception of teachers in the digital age considers the effectiveness of management to be determined by the skills of personal individuals [12]. This is due to the reason for the concept that mastery of personal digital skills [13], [14] closely related to learning success or school management success [14]–[16]. Meanwhile, others consider that solidity or a level of participation can be a trust that can change the management of school management [17].

Overcoming various management problems to be effective requires the cohesiveness of the teacher. The cohesiveness of teachers is said to be an important aspect that can be taken into account as a prerequisite for the effectiveness of primary school management. The statement goes hand in hand with the opinion that the management system is influenced by the commitment of its members. Commitment is an indicator of the attitude of members of the organization that can influence the results of the cooperation of certain goals [18]. However, it is not the only variable that can have a direct impact in realizing management effectiveness. It is precisely because of the many variables that are considered related to the effectiveness of management that management actors have different views on important aspects of school management. There are even teachers who tend to ignore the importance of solidity.

The statement of whether solidity can affect the effectiveness of primary school management, has not yet become a common assumption. In other words, the difference in assumptions arises among the members of the organization (teachers) is regarding the importance of solidity. The existence of differences in assumptions in the midst of the members of the organization is a problem in achieving mutual goal agreements [19]. The solution to this problem is that it needs to be re-examined so that the results can strengthen the statement of whether there is or even how significant the influence between teacher solidity is on the effectiveness of primary school management. So along with this gap, the purpose of this study is to prove how significant the influence of teacher solidity in the digital age is on the effectiveness of elementary school management. Based on the objectives of the study, the formulation of the problem is: how the importance of teacher solidity in the digital age can affect the effectiveness of primary school management? Research on solidity and its relation to changes in school management has been widely carried out [20]–[23]. A notable difference from this newly conducted study is when teacher solidity is related to the digital age.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The solidity of the teacher is closely related to the principle of cohesiveness possessed by the teacher, which is embodied by a sense of universality and humanity, which upholds a sense of community and solidarity in carrying out his duties and obligations as a teacher [24]. Of course, complete teacher solidity is very necessary as well as very influential on the effectiveness of school management, because teachers are an inseparable part of school management activities [25], [26]. The solidity of teachers in this study is, a sense of community, loyalty, and cohesion. Solidity is realized through the ability of teachers to communicate effectively, polite teacher behavior with fellow school residents, effective cooperation with fellow school residents. Solidity also establishes cooperative relationships with fellow professions, superiors, communities, and the business world.

Teacher solidity will affect the effectiveness of school management [27]–[29]. In other opinion, solidity does not significantly affect the success of the group. Because success is determined by other aspects that require professional work skills that are in line with the needs of development in the digital age where success is influenced by individual skills [30]–[32]. It is based on this dissent that the influence of solidity on the effectiveness of primary school management is interesting to review.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with Pearson product moment formula analysis [33] and t-test. Significance is determined with the help of the SPSS program. The variable consists of an independent variable (teacher solidity) (X) and a dependent variable (management effectiveness) (Y). The respondents were 120 teachers in 40 public elementary schools with details of three teachers each school (3x40=120 people). The number of items for measuring the effectiveness of school management variables is 75 items with a value range of 75-375. Where the SD program planning dimensions=23 items with a value range of 23-115; the implementation of the SD work plan=34 items with a value range of 34-170; the supervision and evaluation of SD=13 items with a value range of 14-70; and the SD management information system=5 items with a value range of 5-25. Test the empirical validity of the instrument using the Pearson product moment

correlation formula. The validity test is carried out by comparing the r count with the r table at $\alpha=0.05$ with a 95% confidence level to obtain a valid instrument item. If the r count is greater than the r table ($r \text{ count} > r \text{ table}$) then the instrument is considered valid, and vice versa.

After the try out (TO) instrument with a total of 75 items for the variable effectiveness of school management in 10 public elementary schools in Bengkulu City. The response of 30 teachers can be seen that of the 75 items of school management effectiveness instruments, five instrument items were discarded or dropped because the r count was smaller than $r \text{ table}=0.632$, namely numbers 9, 13, 25, 28, and 31, so that they were aborted or not used. While 70 items are received (valid) because the r count value is greater than $r \text{ table}=0.632$ with a confidence level of 95%. Test the reliability of the instrument using the Cronbach alpha formula after a valid instrument item is obtained, while the invalid instrument item is discarded. In this case, if the $r \text{ count} > r \text{ table}$ then the instrument grain is said to be reliable, and vice versa.

Data analysis of teacher solidity variables with the number of principals (respondents) as many as 40 people for 40 public elementary schools as a research analysis unit. Test the empirical validity of the instrument using Pearson's product moment correlation formula. The validity test is performed by comparing the r count with table r at $\alpha=0.05$ with a confidence level of 95% to obtain a valid instrument item. If the r count is greater than the r table ($r \text{ calculates} > r \text{ of the table}$) then the instrument is considered valid, and vice versa. After trying TO, the instrument with a total of 32 items of teacher solidity variables in 10 public elementary schools in Bengkulu City, with the response of 10 principals can be known from 32 items of teacher solidity instruments, there are three instrument items that were discarded or dropped because the count of r was smaller than $r \text{ table}=0.632$, namely the numbers 1, 24, and 25, so that it is aborted or unused. Whereas 29 items are received (valid) because the r count value is greater than $r \text{ table}=0.632$ with a confidence level of 95%.

The data analysis technique is carried out after the data is obtained, then continued with the tabulation of the data to be analyzed starting with a statistical description including frequency, average, standard deviation, median, mode, bar chart (histogram), and the percentage of respondent assessment for each research variable data. For the estimation of the error normality test using the Lilliefors test and a simple regression linearity test between two variables to check the data whether it is distributed normally or not. The testing of this data analysis requirement is carried out with the help of computer program data analysis in the form of Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS). For a simple correlation test in analyzing two variables, namely X to Y , Pearson's product moment correlation formula is used. Furthermore, in order to test the significance of the influence, that is, whether the influence found applies to the entire population, it is necessary to test its significance with the formula t test with the hypothesis: $H_0: \beta_1 \leq 0$; $H_1: \beta_1 > 0$.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the analysis on the effect of teacher solidity on the effectiveness of state elementary school management throughout Bengkulu City, it can be described as data in the form of mean values, median, mode, standard deviation, variance, range, minimum score, maximum score, total score, frequency distribution, and accompanied by a histogram (bar chart). The results of the summary of the data description can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Recapitulation of the data description of each variable

	Teacher solidity (X)	Effectiveness of school management (Y)
N Valid	40	40
Missing	0	0
Mean	114.30	298.8460
Median	117.50	295.7250
Mode	125	272.92
Std. Deviation	19.983	21.10913
Variance	398.523	445.59535
Range	55	91.82
Minimum	85	240.61
Maximum	140	332.43
Sum	4572	11873.84

4.1. Effectiveness of school management

Data on the effectiveness of school management was obtained from a questionnaire containing 70 items with a score of numbers 1 to 5. Theoretically, the score range ranges from 70 to 350. Table 2 shows that the probability of the lowest score is 70 and the highest score is 350. The results of data quantification from 120 respondents (teachers) for the analysis unit of 40 elementary schools (by taking the average data

quantification results from three respondents for each elementary school) the range of empirical scores between the lowest score of 240.61 to the highest score of 332.43. When viewed in terms of the tendency to concentrate data, the mean is 296.84, the median is 295.72, and the mode is 272.92. Judging from the number of respondents who have a score above the mean of 18 people (45%) which is the highest score. It can be concluded that on average the effectiveness of school management in the category is good. Then when viewed in terms of the tendency of data dispersal, the standard deviation of 21.10, the variance of 445.59 and the range of 91.82 were obtained. Then, the data on the frequency distribution of the effectiveness of school management of state elementary school Bengkulu City can be seen in Figure 1.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of school management effectiveness scores

No	School management effectiveness score	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	240-253	1	2.50
2	254-267	1	2.50
3	268-281	12	30.00
4	282-295	10	25.00
5	296-311	4	10.00
6	310-325	10	25.00
7	324-337	2	5.00
***	***	40	100

Figure 1. Histogram of frequency distribution of school management effectiveness

4.2. Teacher solidity

Teacher solidity data was obtained from a questionnaire containing 29 items with a score of numbers 1 to 5. Theoretically, the score range ranges from 29 to 145. To obtain a clear picture the following is shown as in Table 3. Based on table, the lowest score probability is 29 and the highest score is 145. The results of data quantification from 40 respondents obtained a range of empirical scores between the lowest score of 85 to the highest score of 140. When viewed in terms of the tendency to concentrate data, an average of 114.30, a median of 117.5, and a mode of 125 were obtained. In terms of data distribution trends, standard deviations of 19.96, variances of 398.52, and ranges of 55 were obtained. Then, the frequency distribution of teacher solidity can be seen on Figure 2.

Table 3. Frequency distribution of teacher solidity scores

No	Teacher Solidity Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	85-93	13	32.50
2	94-102	1	2.50
3	103-111	3	7.50
4	112-120	5	12.50
5	121-129	6	15.00
6	130-138	7	17.50
7	139-147	5	12.50
***	***	40	100

Figure 2. Teacher solidity frequency distribution histogram

Based on Figure 2, it can be known that there are 13 frequencies for scores between 85-93, there are one frequency for scores between 94-102, there are three frequencies for scores between 103-111, there are five frequencies for scores between 112-120, there are six frequencies for scores between 121-129, there are seven frequencies for scores between 130-138, and there are five frequencies for scores between 139-147. Normality testing is carried out with Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Kz) statistics, with a significant level used is $\alpha=0.05$ as a condition for accepting or rejecting normal testing or not of a data distribution. The results of the standard error test estimate the effectiveness of school management (Y) on teacher solidity (X) can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of normality testing results

No	Error estimating regression Y over X	Rated L count	At n = 40 L table $\alpha =0.05$	Decision
3.	Y over X	0.1290	0.1401	Normally distributed

The results of the normality test obtained $L_{count} < L_{table}$ so that it can be concluded that the data of the free variable of the study, namely teacher solidity, shows that at a significant level of 0.05, the research data comes from a population that is normally distributed and hypothesis testing can be carried out. To test the linearity of the research data a hypothesis was proposed: Distribution of independent variable test pairs over linearly patterned dependent variables (H0); Distribution of independent variable test pairs over non-linearly patterned dependent variables (H1). Based on the calculation results using SPSS 16.00 for Windows obtained ANOVA table for linearity test as presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Summary of regression linearity test results

Test Pairs	Test F	Significance	Alpha	Condition	Conclusion
Y over X	1.246	0.307	0.05	Sig>Alpha	Linier

Based on ANOVA analysis, the results of the regression linearity test in Table 5, the F value calculated at the deviation from linearity for the school management effectiveness variable test pair (Y) on the teacher solidity variable (X) of 1.246 with a sig value $=0.307 > (=0.05)$. Thus, it can be said that the results of hypothesis testing on the linearity of the score of the test pair of school management effectiveness variables (Y) over the teacher solidity variable (X) received H0. So, it can be concluded that the distribution of variable test pairs of school management effectiveness (Y) over teacher solidity (X) linear patterned distribution. Furthermore, the results of the calculation of teacher solidity (X) affect the effectiveness of school management (Y) can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Summary of coefficient results

Influence between variables	Coefficient (Beta)	Calculated t-value	Calculated F value	Test results	Coefficient of Determination R_2	Coefficient other variables (residual)
X_3 towards Y	0.337	2.630	37.692	H_0 rejected	0.759	0.241

Based on Table 6, the statistical hypothesis proposed in relation to teacher solidity (X) has a direct positive effect on the effectiveness of school management (Y) is: H_0 ($YX \leq 0$); H_1 ($YX > 0$). Based on the results of the calculation of the coefficient value (PYX) of 0.337 with t count=2.630 and sig.=0.012, while the t table value=2.028 at (0.05 with the degree of freedom (dk)=36. Since t count =2.630 is greater than t table=2.028, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted and the coefficient is significant, meaning that teacher solidity has a direct positive effect on the effectiveness of school management as can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Hypothesis testing recapitulation

No	Hypothesis	Statistical Test	T test		Conclusion
			T_{count}	t_{table}	
1	Teacher solidity (X) has a direct positive effect on the effectiveness of school management (Y)	$H_0: \beta_{YX} \leq 0$ $H_1: \beta_{YX} > 0$	2.630	2.028	Positive direct effect

Based on the results of hypothesis testing on Table 7, it was found that teacher solidity had a direct positive effect on the effectiveness of school management. This means that the higher the solidity of teachers, the higher the effectiveness of school management. On the other hand, the lower the solidity of teachers, the lower the effectiveness of school management. The findings of this study show the urgency of the influence of teacher solidity factors on the effectiveness of school management as can be seen from the correlation of 0.337 at a real level (0.05). This means that there is a positive direct influence of teacher solidity on the effectiveness of the management of public elementary schools throughout Bengkulu City.

The effectiveness of school management can be influenced by factors that are elements of management [34]. Elements in management include the solidity of its members and supportive leadership. With regard to the urgency of the influence of the teacher solidity factor on the effectiveness of school management, teachers need to increase the sense of solidity [35] (cohesiveness and togetherness) through effective communication, polite behavior with fellow school residents, effective cooperation with fellow school residents, and establishing cooperative relationships with fellow professions, superiors, communities, and the business world.

The results of this study also answer doubts about the presence or absence of the influence of solidity on the effectiveness of school management. The doubt is caused by the assumption that there is a significant shift in which 'solidity' no longer plays a role in improving the effectiveness of school management. This view considers those elements of the professional world that rely on personal skills as a condition for achieving the goals of effective management. Based on the results of the study, it is understood that teacher solidity even though living in the digital era must still place teacher solidity in improving the effectiveness of school management, including increasing teacher professionalism [36] needs to be prioritized. However, individual skills in mastering theology are still required [37] in facing the challenges of life needs in the digital world. It is intended that there is mutual cooperation, the content of filling in each other's constraints in the management of school institutions that are more effective from various dimensions of teacher ability [38]–[40].

Dimensions of the teacher's ability to communicate effectively include the ability to communicate [36] with staff, fellow teachers, principals, parents, and the community. The dimensions of polite teacher behavior with fellow school residents include polite behavior [41] with staff, fellow teachers, and principals. Dimensions of effective cooperation with fellow school residents [42] including effective cooperation with staff, fellow teachers, principals. The dimensions of establishing cooperative relationships with residents outside the school include cooperation with fellow provinces, superiors, communities, and the business world.

Furthermore, the implication of the findings of this study is that because teacher solidity has a direct positive effect on the effectiveness of school management, to improve the effectiveness of school management, efforts are made to improve teacher solidity. Improving teacher solidity requires an increased sense of solidity [43] (cohesiveness and togetherness). Strengthening the meaning of the essence of humanity [44] spirituality that cannot be separated from man's need for God [45]. Realizing human life cannot be separated from the interaction of mutual needs of fellow humans in a tolerant manner [46], [47], so it is necessary to constantly strengthen the attitude aspect. Reinforcement can be done by continuing to educate

yourself. Meanwhile, in terms of social interaction needs, it is necessary to develop digital-based communication skills. Communication skills [12], [48], [49] which can be done effectively as one such effort. Polite behavior [50] with fellow school residents need to be noted. Effective cooperation needs to be carried out with fellow school residents, fellow provinces, superiors, communities, and the business world. Building a solid education system does not mean anti-digital; education that leads to holistic learning [51] is the integration of the solid attitude of teachers supported by individual skills to welcome the atmosphere of the education system in the digital era.

Dimensions of the teacher's ability to communicate [52] effectively includes the ability to communicate with staff, fellow teachers, principals, parents, and the community. Dimensions of polite teacher behavior [53] with fellow school residents including polite behavior with staff, fellow teachers, and principals. Dimensions of effective cooperation with fellow school residents including effective cooperation with staff, fellow teachers, principals [54]. The dimensions of establishing cooperative relationships with residents outside of school include cooperation with fellow provinces [17], superiors, society, and the business world. Furthermore, efforts to improve the social competence of teachers are very important. This can be done through education and training (training), seminars, and others in order to increase teacher solidity which includes the ability to interact, communicate, associate with the school environment community and the community of the environment where they live.

5. CONCLUSION

As already explained, the results of this study can be concluded that teacher solidity has a direct positive effect on the effectiveness of school management. The difference in the assumption of shifting the role of 'teacher solidity in improving the effectiveness of school management' was resolved by the results of this study. The loss of differences in assumptions will make the management atmosphere will further strengthen solidarity among teachers. The creation of teacher solidarity will increase the effectiveness of school management. The implication of the results of such research is that the integration of individual skills along with the development of digital communication with an attitude of solidity will become increasingly needed. This need is considered important considering that education in the future will be increasingly faced with the challenges of an all-digital era but does not leave an attitude of cohesiveness as a teacher to build the effectiveness of good school management. Future research suggestions are the importance of disclosing data through research related to the ability and awareness of teachers simultaneously and integrately related to solidity and development of communication skills in building school management needed in the digital era.

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